

A review of the management of teacher training

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Abstract

Teacher quality in general and the Management of Teacher training, in particular, have been becoming interested much more than ever by researchers all over the world because these issues are always regarded as the keys to any quality education system. A review method is used in this paper in order to find out what has been researched in the management of teacher training. The findings show that there are three main focuses of the research assessment and evaluation, forms of training or training delivery and this sector has been researched in some countries. There are further studies on the issue and its relevant characteristics should be carried out that can make futuristic contributions to the management of teacher training.

Keywords: Teacher quality; Training management; Teacher training; Teacher quality

1. Introduction

In schools, teachers are the ones who directly put theoretical knowledge into educational practice. The moral quality, cognitive level, and creative thinking ability of learners not only depend on the curriculum and textbooks, on the learning environment at school, but also on their quality and personality. Teachers' professional qualifications and abilities The role of teachers in today's era has undergone fundamental changes, marking a turning point in pedagogical work. In addition, the level of awareness, the will to strive to excel at work, self-study, and self-improvement regularly to improve the professional qualifications of each teacher should aim to standardize the level of training and education. Meeting professional standards contributes significantly to improving the quality of the staff and improving the effectiveness of education.

Education is more than just a tool; it is also a human expectation to pass on ideals to the next generation. Teachers have a critical role in driving this transformation in education. However, the changing educational landscape necessitates new attributes in instructors in order to adapt to these changes. To date, several kinds of research on trainer management in developing nations have been conducted as a foundation for addressing the requirements of instructors in these countries, mostly linked to managing teacher shortages. A teacher shortage exists. As a result, the analysis of these works will contribute to a review of the research directions of teacher training management while also helping to improve the quality of teaching staff and bringing efficiency to educational systems. The researches are assessment and evaluation [15], [11], [7], [12], [4], [8], [6]; forms of training [10], [5], [1], [17], [16], [13]; nationally [9], [1], [3], [2], [14].

2. Material and methods

The review method is used to conduct this research, it is because it provides general information on the management of teacher training and it is because it is a useful way to see the interests of the authors/researchers in the period of

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time or in the particular domain of management. The documents were collected from the internet and classified into main categories including assessment and evaluation, forms of training, and management of teacher training in some countries. This way of conducting the research has not gained whole relevant documents or data from the databases, but it is worth doing by selecting the quality research to study.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The assessment and evaluation

And the personality assessment was regarded as the method to manage teacher training [11], it is obvious that instructors conduct personality assessments during interviews and that this assessment impacts selection. In general, their comments on the forms suggest that they take this seriously. Tutors try to put candidates at ease and give them every opportunity to shine; for example, a number of forms mention candidates' initial nervousness, but this had no effect on the final outcome, and the word "nervous" is only included in the categories if it refers to a specific and persistent quality (e.g., "too nervous a disposition"). Despite unfavorable assessments and frequently competent candidates, every eliminated candidate had something nice to say about them. In general, the remarks about rejected candidates are fuller and more individual than those about accepted candidates. The expressions tutors record on the interview form may differ in detail, but the DES-defined traits are measured, and the students chosen are regarded to have those qualities to a higher extent than those rejected. The insights gained from comparing interview assessments with course outcomes show that interviewers not only take this obligation seriously, but also carry it out successfully in terms of later performance in practical teaching.

It is noticeable that the DES-defined criteria are assessed [12], despite unfavorable judgements and often qualifications, every eliminated candidates had something nice mentioned about them. In general, statements regarding rejected candidates are more detailed and personal than those about selected candidates. The expressions tutors record on the interview form may range in detail language, but the DES-defined criteria are assessed, and the students chosen are considered to exhibit those qualities to a larger degree than those rejected. The insights gained from comparing interview assessments with course outcomes show that not only do interviewers take this role seriously, but they also carry it out successfully in terms of later performance in practical teaching.

Professional competence and performance assessments were considered as the effective ways of management of teacher training [4]. It is critical to assess learners in the clinical situation in order to determine their degree of professional competence. In-training evaluation reports can be used to document clinical performance assessments (ITERS). Previous study has indicated that faculty development is required to increase the quality of these reports. Previous study revealed critical features of high-quality finished ITERS, specifically the narrative remarks. This is consistent with contemporary assessment literature emphasis on the importance of qualitative evaluations. There is evidence that professors can be educated to complete higher-quality ITERS. We propose 12 critical methods for clinical supervisors to help them improve the quality of their completed ITERS. Higher quality completed ITERS will enhance trainee progress documentation and be more defensible when questioned in court.

In the case study in 2015 at Malaysia [8], investigated and evaluated the quality and efficacy of information literacy training used by teacher trainees in their subsequent research process. A sample of teacher trainees enrolled at Malaysian Teacher Education Institutes in Malaysia's northern area was polled. The objective of these institutions is to prepare instructors who will have a thorough and accurate grasp of information literacy fundamental principles and skills and will be able to use those core concepts and skills in their different follow-up research procedures. Many contemporary observers have stated that many, if not the majority, of prospective Malaysian teachers start teaching practice without having sufficiently learnt the requisite basic information literacy concepts and abilities, which may subsequently be used implicitly in their subsequent research processes. Based on the results, conclusions, and suggestions of the case study, the report offers many improvements that are required in official Malaysian teacher training policies, programs, and curriculum. The authors created and used an Information Literacy Research Process Model in this case study to describe and explain trainee behaviors in searching for, retrieving, organizing, evaluating, and applying the obtained information wisely and ethically, using learned information literacy core principles and skills. The researchers investigated these behaviors within the framework of the Malaysian teacher training syllabus, which is adopted by all Malaysian training institutes. A sample of teacher trainees was chosen from many of these institutes located in the country's northern area. This was accomplished through the use of a "mixed approaches" design.

The research was carried out in the 2015 by Elassy, with the development and implementation of a questionnaire to assess student satisfaction at Liverpool John Moores University's Faculty of Business and Law. The survey questionnaire was designed using the service-product bundle idea, and the findings were analyzed using SPSS and Quadrant Analysis

to discover which components of the University's services were most significant and the degree to which they pleased the students. The most significant features were those related to teaching and learning, whereas those related to physical amenities were the least important. The service-product bundle idea is a viable and reliable technique for designing a satisfaction survey and segmenting a University's service offering in such a way that management may concentrate resources at regions thought to have low satisfaction and high relevance. Most educational institutions can use the questionnaire. Using the service-product bundle idea lays the burden of questionnaire content and design squarely on the service provider rather than the consumer [6].

Obviously, the assessment and evaluation of management of teacher training have been various and widely used in the researches from 1991 to 2015. It was started with personality assessment to the DES-defined criteria, Professional competence and performance assessments, the quality and efficacy of information literacy training, and student satisfaction.

3.2. Forms of training

In the year 1985, the research was conducted as part of an attempt to improve instruction and combine special and regular education, five New York City school districts established in-service programs. The quality of these programs was evaluated in this study using criteria drawn from evaluations of literature on effective in-service education. For ten features of quality in-service education, there was agreement in the literature. The five districts' analysis of in-service education revealed that training for classroom special education teachers lacked the majority of the characteristics of quality in-service training, whereas training for administrators and resource room teachers met many of the criteria found in effective in-service education. One of the barriers to offering effective in-service programs to classroom instructors was a shortage of training time [15].

In the research in 2005, [5] decentralization is frequently assumed to boost democratic participation and empowerment while also increasing government responsiveness to local concerns. International experience shows that striking the right balance between centralisation and decentralisation remains difficult, and that developing appropriate institutional capacity to discharge new responsibilities is difficult and often overlooked - despite the fact that both are critical to effective decentralisation. Using a case study of six district institutes of education and training (DIETs) from three states, this research investigates India's policies and methods for decentralizing teacher education. It cites recruiting and personnel rules, as well as contentious agendas of power, control, and responsibility, as important hurdles to the establishment of DIETs. However, it finds evidence from two districts of progress toward building fruitful partnerships, as part of an increasing decentralisation movement that allows DIETs to play a substantial role in helping teachers. The DIET concept is validated in this paper, and the possibility of a decentralized teacher education system to promote systemic responsibility for quality improvement and primary teachers is proven.

With the study implemented by Cantoni (2006) to demonstrates the significance of information and communication technologies in the field of education for developing countries. The opportunities they give for teacher training in disadvantaged communities are discussed, and some examples from the Brazilian context are provided to demonstrate the relevance of three primary issues: Access, Impact, and Quality. The report also discusses the BET-K12 project framework, emphasizing how it incorporates the aforementioned concerns, which are important not just for creating solid research but, more importantly, for the efficacy, efficiency, and sustainability of development-related activities [1].

To prove the roles of wikis, Wheel considers writing as a social practice and speculates on how wikis may be utilized to foster higher-quality academic writing and collaborative learning. This investigation of the online learning activities of undergraduate teacher trainees focuses on how shared spaces - wikis - may be utilized to discuss ideas and develop course-specific content. The study also looked into how such activities helped students enhance their academic writing abilities and engage in more critical learning. Student impressions of the utility of wikis in support of their academic studies were mapped using data from student discussion boards and a post-module email questionnaire (n = 35). The findings show that most students improved their writing skills when they wrote directly to the publicly available wiki area, as opposed to the more casual text they submitted on the discussion boards. Due to students' unwillingness to edit each other's work, the breadth of collaborative writing was restricted, but students valued the shared environment as a method of discussing their work and the course subject. Students claimed that their formal engagement in the wiki had enhanced their academic writing skills [17].

Especially, physical activity participation tracks from infancy and adolescence into adulthood, implying that the time to act is early in life to reap the various health advantages of physical activity. Implementing high-quality school-based physical education is one technique that has been shown to be beneficial in boosting physical activity levels in children and adolescents in both high-income and low- and middle-income nations (PE). Given the demonstrated usefulness of

this technique in boosting population levels of physical activity in this age range, it is critical to understand existing school-based PE policy. As a result, the objective of this study is to outline the policies now in place in nations throughout the world for mandating PE as part of primary or secondary school curriculum. Data on school-based PE were gathered using the World Data on Education website of the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization. Data on whether or not PE lessons were included in each country's national school curriculum were collected separately for primary (grade levels 1-8) and secondary (grade levels 9 and beyond) education. In the case of a yes response, it was determined whether or not the number of days per week is pre-defined and/or minutes per week in PE are specified. Data on the number of minutes per week spent in PE were available for 161 primary nations and 155 secondary nations. Data on class sessions per week were acquired for 126 nations at the primary level and 136 countries at the secondary level. Two nations do not require physical education in elementary school, and 18 do not require it in high school. PE is required in all high-income countries, but not in 5.0 percent of upper-middle income countries, 17.8 percent of lower-middle income countries, or 27.6 percent of low-income countries. This study uncovered ongoing gaps in PE standards, particularly in low-income nations. While the information currently available about PE in schools aids in understanding global policies, a surveillance system specifically designed for monitoring the existence, quality, and implementation of PE policies is required to more accurately evaluate the effects of such policies on physical activity and health. This information is critical as policymakers and school administrators decide how much, how frequently, and what sort of PE programs to implement [16].

And Sibgatullina discusses how modern technology may be used to improve the quality of teacher education (as exemplified by the training of foreign language teachers). The author explores the notion of "quality of education," suggests, and evaluates criteria for measuring the quality of education of prospective foreign language instructors. The use of the methods and techniques described below in the training of future teachers (information and communication technologies, remote technologies, e-learning, activity-based learning, and others) should, in the author's opinion, contribute to the development of the teacher's professional competence [13].

Generally, it can be said that there are some forms of training delivery that management of teacher training have been researched and mentioned by authors, that are a shortage of training time of in-service education, decentralization, the significance of information and communication technologies, the roles of wikis, physical activity participation, and criteria for measuring the quality.

3.3. The scope of nation

That was the teacher training programs of Botswana, [9] the overarching argument of this research is that external variables, such as university affiliation, may be leveraged to improve teacher training programs. The specific challenges raised concern quality control and assurance. As an example, the University of Botswana (UB) is given. Concepts and terminology are presented, and the critical function of quality control and assurance is described and explored. Their influence is assessed in three areas: courses provided, final tests, and teaching practice. The UB system's operational problems, both present, and potential are examined. The developed argument is that the existing quality control techniques should be supplemented by more effective quality assurance. The report finishes by highlighting the benefits received and the ramifications for governments.

The study conducted by Cantoni to demonstrates the significance of information and communication technologies in the education of developing countries. The opportunities they present for teacher training in underserved regions are discussed, and some examples from the Brazilian context are provided to demonstrate the significance of three primary issues: Access, Impact, and Quality. The report also defines the BET-K12 project framework, emphasizing how it incorporates the aforementioned concerns, which are important not just for conducting solid research but, more importantly, for the efficacy, efficiency, and sustainability of actions aimed at fostering development [1].

In the research at Queensland, the building of a new learning future is both a problem and an opportunity for today's learners and educators. Making meaning by and for all participants in the educational endeavor is a critical component of that creation. The performance of practice - that is, the regular, repeated enactment of situated learning and teaching in specific situations and surroundings that transform abstract and speculative notions about education into actual and lived realities - is also important in producing meaning. This study applies and shows this reasoning in regard to a suite of teacher education programs at the University of Southern Queensland (USQ) in Australia. The authors provide a series of evaluating questions for the leadership, quality, and technological elements of those programs' curriculum. Based on these issues, the authors provide a conceptual framework that they say is useful for identifying the principles and techniques of meaning creating and performing practice that are most likely to foster the development of new and enabling learning futures [3].

A research was done in Cambodia (2014), that considers a competent teacher is an essential pillar for improving student learning outcomes and educational quality. The purpose of this article is to investigate Cambodian teachers' perspectives of (1) teacher competency and enhancing education quality; and (2) assuring teacher quality and in-service teacher training. A questionnaire was employed in this study, which addressed a line of educational employees in Cambodia, from school to central level. In August of 2012, 230 copies were circulated, with 173 copies collected (75.22 percent). It was revealed via concerned notice that the majority of higher-ranking authorities had also worked at any school education level. As a result, it was discovered that (a) respondents recognized and explicitly stated that competent teachers help contribute to students' learning and promote the level of education quality; and (b) respondents recognized the importance of in-service training because it helps teachers become more confident in their profession by earning people's respect and trust. This article concludes that Cambodian teachers recognize the importance of their work. They also want to improve their capabilities through continual professional development and in-service training programs. As a result, developing a workable in-service training approach for them is clearly required. The anticipated structure will be organized in line with Cambodia's current circumstances and available resources [2]. In Nepal (2015), inadequate transfer of information, skills, attitudes, and behaviors from the classroom to the workplace has arisen as a global problem. Teachers' education has been no exception. According to the available research on teacher education, the contribution of training may be measured on at least six dimensions: quality, access, equality, efficiency, teacher development, and overall school improvement. Studies on teacher training or teacher professional development in Nepal have also revealed a lack of sufficient transfer of information and skills from training to the workplace. There are various elements that might help or hinder the scope of such a transfer. According to research, teacher training has contributed to and can positively influence educational quality if stakeholders are made aware of and well informed about the quality and relevance of carefully designed and implemented training and development interventions for the capacity development of teachers, teacher educators, or trainers. This article is based on a summary of a comprehensive research done in Nepal and completed in March 2010. The databases of 4033 trained instructors from 45 schools in 25 different sample districts were investigated. This study included both quantitative and qualitative methods. There were nine education specialists and 22 field researchers participating. The author was the study's team leader. The sole academic goal of this article is to inspire excellence in teaching, learning, and performance via the professionalism and capacity building of teachers, teacher trainers, and their employers [14].

Clearly, the management of teacher training has been implemented and researched in many countries both developed and developing once. Each country has its own problems with the management of teacher training, Botswana is external variables, Brasilia is information and communication technologies, Australia is the performance of the practice, Cambodia is a workable in-service training approach, and Nepal is the transfer of information and skills.

4. Conclusion

The research on teacher training management was carried out very early and has continued to attract the attention of scientists in recent years. Research topics and problems are quite diverse depending on the context or research conditions in each different project. The forms of assessment are diverse and gradually shift towards competence and performance assessment. However, there are many aspects of overlap between the studies as reflected in the research issues and research findings, such as competence and performance, criteria and standards, and limitations of the work. Information technology and practical skills, etc. It is noteworthy that these commonalities are in different contexts, so it is difficult to find similarities. In short, the changes in education today are demanding an increasingly important role in the quality of the teacher. And this is also a challenge for pedagogical schools.

This study has limitations in data and scope, but the authors have tried to give general points as well as specific features of the works based on the data obtained and selected for study and analysis. Furthermore, there is a need for studies with this same trend but at a more in-depth level and a larger scope or scale to be able to make more accurate judgments and have an overall picture of educational management and training to this day.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare. All co-authors have seen and agree with the contents of the manuscript.

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